

RELAZIONE PROGETTO BIO-NRG STORE

Periodo 15/12/22 al 31/08/23

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Durata : 14/12/20-14/07/24*

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OGGETTO: Programma cooperazione internazionale "BIO-NRG-STORE Bio-Based Phase Change Materials in Lignocellulose Matrix for Energy Storage in Buildings".

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Con riguardo alla Vs comunicazione pervenuta in data, si prende atto della estensione della durata del progetto di 7 mesi, senza aggravio di costi ed in linea con quanto stabilito a livello internazionale.

IL DIRIGENTE

Dott. Michele Mazzola

Documento firmato digitalmente ai sensi del c.d. Codice dell'Amministrazione Digitale e normativa connessa.

1 Obiettivi realizzativi

In questa relazione finale dal 15/12/22 al 31/08/23 sono riportati gli avanzamenti della ricerca nell'ambito del progetto BIO NRG STORE.

Sono riportate le attività svolte progettuali ed i risultati ottenuti fino ad adesso rispetto agli obiettivi realizzativi:

- 1. OR1 (WP 4.1) Assemblaggio di prototipi abitativi (BOXES MODEL) per testare le proprietà chimico-fisiche dei bio-compositi con PCMs.**

2. **OR3 (WP 3.3) Proprietà termomeccaniche dei bio-compositi con PCMs.**
3. **OR4 (WP 3-4) Valutazione della durabilità alle muffe in condizioni di laboratorio dei bio-compositi con PCM.**
4. **OR4 (WP 3-4) Valutazione della durabilità ai funghi della carie in condizioni di laboratorio dei bio-compositi con PCM.**
5. **OR4 (WP 3-4) Valutazione della durabilità alle termiti in condizioni di laboratorio dei bio-compositi con PCM.**
6. **OR1 (WP 4.2) Realization of fungal mycelium with PCM prototypes**

1. OR1 (WP 4.1) Assembly of wooden boxes to test the chemical-physical properties of PCMs.

1.1 Introduction

The activity of assembling the boxes that regards the international commune part of project started from 01. December 2022.

First CNR IBE bought all the raw materials necessary under the indication of leader partners Austria: OSB and plywood panels, roofing sheets, wood fiber panels, windows and all the parts that led to the assembly of the box. Then all the assembling part was made in the workshop of CNR IBE with the active participation of Mechanical and Physical Laboratory.

Before to start the assembling the boxes, dr Andrea Atena attended a training activity at the University of Applied Science, Kuchl Salzburg, both for the assembly of the structure and for the setting of the sensors. Further during the construction of the boxes the Austrian partners participated to the checking of the boxes at CNR IBE. Many researchers participated to the assembling part of these, Paolo Burato, Giovanni Aminti and Andrea Atena (CNR IBE) were

involved directly in this activity. Further especially for sensors and computer part put into the boxes for monitoring the physical parameters, Dr Fabio De Francesco, CNR IBE was and still continue to follow this part of the project.

2 Material and methods

The material that was used for the construction of the wooden boxes (Figure 5.) was the following:

- 15 meters of cover sheet for the roof and base of the boxes;
- 75 wood fiber panels for wall insulation;
- 4 OSB panels measuring 2.35 x 2.35 m for the interior;
- 8 plywood panels of 1.35 x 1.35 m for the construction of the base;
- Solid wood for the construction of the boxes base;
- 2 glass windows with air chamber;
- Insulating paint and all necessary components.

Two wooden boxes were built, one to test the PCM panels (Figure 1), assembled by the Swedish partner and a control box with OSB panels. The PCM panels that have been introduced into the boxes have a size of 50x50 cm, for a surface of 1 m².

In each of the boxes there is a computer (Figure 1) with the settings of the 11 sensors (Figure 2) foreseen for monitoring the characteristics of the PCMs. PCMs structure is made by rest of newspapers, fabric, scraps of paper and wetted with an acid ESTER.

The trend of the data is reported daily by an remote software (Figure 3), where all the project partners can follow the results in real time. The monitoring time of the WP4, is about 1 year and coordinated by the Austrian partner.

Below are the photos of the construction of the wooden boxes and their final location, inside the patio of the CNR.

Figure 1 Bio-composite panel

Figure 2. Computer box for the monitoring.

Figure 3. Computer box for the monitoring

Figures 4. Sensors for the setting.

Figure 5. Remote software for the monitoring.

Figure 6. Model box during the assembling

Figure 7. Model box during the assembling

Figure 8. Model box during the assembling

Figure 9. Model box during the assembling

Figure 10. Model box during the assembling

Figure 11. Model box during the assembling

Figure 12. Model box placed in patio of CNR

Figure

Figure 14. Wooden boxes with PCM, inside view with the position of sensors

Figure 15. Wooden boxes with OSB internal view with the position of sensors

The data acquisition started on 30 April 2023.

The first acquisitions are reported in the following figures and tables.

Figure 16 Morning trend boxes temperatures from 6.00 to 12.00.

Figure 17 Temperatures during the day from 13:00 to 19:00.

Figure 18 Temperatures during the night since 20:00 to 5:00.

Table 1 Morning Temperature 6:00-12:00

Day	Temp reference	Temp PCM	Temp outside
01/05/2023	21,7	22,1	20,4
02/05/2023	18,8	19,6	19,3

03/05/2023	18,3	22,5	21,4
04/05/2023	19,8	23,4	24,1
05/05/2023	20,5	24,9	25,3
06/05/2023	20,6	24,9	25,1
07/05/2023	21,0	25,2	26,1
08/05/2023	21,3	24,8	26,2
09/05/2023	21,7	25,9	26,5
10/05/2023	23,1	22,4	19,7
11/05/2023	17,9	20,8	20,6
12/05/2023	18,6	19,3	17,5
13/05/2023	18,6	18,5	17,2
14/05/2023	18,7	17,7	16,9

TABLE 2 Temperature during the day 13:00 19:00

Day	Temp reference	Temp PCM	Temp outside
01/05/2023	19,7	19,0	18,2
02/05/2023	18,9	18,5	18,0
03/05/2023	22,5	20,8	18,8
04/05/2023	24,7	22,0	17,0
05/05/2023	25,1	21,9	16,8
06/05/2023	25,7	22,6	17,6

07/05/2023	25,4	22,4	17,7
08/05/2023	25,4	22,8	18,1
09/05/2023	26,3	24,3	19,6
10/05/2023	19,8	18,5	14,8
11/05/2023	20,8	19,9	17,2
12/05/2023	18,6	18,8	17,3
13/05/2023	18,7	18,0	17,0
14/05/2023	18,7	17,2	16,7

TABLE 3 Temperature during the night 22:00 5:00

Day	Temp reference	Temp PCM	Temp outside
01/05/2023	19,7	19,0	18,2
02/05/2023	18,9	18,5	18,0
03/05/2023	22,5	20,8	18,8
04/05/2023	24,7	22,0	17,0
05/05/2023	25,1	21,9	16,8
06/05/2023	25,7	22,6	17,6
07/05/2023	25,4	22,4	17,7
08/05/2023	25,4	22,8	18,1
09/05/2023	26,3	24,3	19,6
10/05/2023	19,8	18,5	14,8

11/05/2023	20,8	19,9	17,2
12/05/2023	18,6	18,8	17,3
13/05/2023	18,7	18,0	17,0
14/05/2023	18,7	17,2	16,7

Figure 19 PCM leached out on the floor.

Figure

3.1 Troubles

By this first acquisition it was possible to note that:

During the morning and the day, afternoon, the difference between OSB and bio-composite impregnated with PCM was very small, only during the night it was possible appreciate a slight difference.

During the last summer 23, the temperatures reaches high values (always more than 25) with the consequences that the PCM impregnated in wooden floor leached out.

To solve these problems it was covered the window with a white curtain;

Mitigating the high summer temperatures was the priority to preserve the functionality of PCM panels. It is expected that, in September, when temperatures will return to mitigate, if the

properties of the panels are not altered by the dispersion of PCM liquid, the operation of the panels can resume normally.

2. OR3 (WP3.1 e WP 3.3) Thermomechanical properties *Bio-based Phase Change Materials in Lignocellulose Matrix for energy Store in Building 1.*

2.1 Foreword

This report covers the activities carried out within Work Package 3.3 of Operational Objective 3 (Thermomechanical Properties). Specifically, the report describes the tests carried out to assess the internal cohesive strength of the insulation panels produced by the Swedish team using ethyl palmitate ester as the bio-phase-change material, impregnated into Scots pine wood particles. The aim of the tests was not to reach a minimum bonding strength threshold, as this is not usually provided for in insulation materials, but to assess the internal bond (IB) quality of the panel in case of possible comparisons with other similar panels made with other materials, in order to make quantitative type evaluations².

2.2 Materials and method

The panels on which the tests were carried out were produced by the Swedish team. There were two panels with dimensions of ca. 9 x 520 x 520 mm³. They were made using ethyl palmitate ester (EP) as the bio-phase-change material, impregnated into wood particles of Scots pine. In particular, EP was added to both sapwood and heartwood particles. The percentage of EP + wood particles was 50% (i.e. 25% EP and 25% particles) of the total composite. A non-impregnated recycled newspaper (RNP) was added to the wood particles and EP, in order to prevent possible leaching of EP (the paper is supposed to absorb the EP) and the percentage of RNP was 12.5% of the total composite mass. Finally, a polymerised epoxidized linseed oil was used as the binder in a proportion of 37.5% of the total composite mass (the amount of the catalyst, being less than 1%, has been neglected).

The appearance of the panels before their characterisation is shown in Figure 1.

On the other hand, the panels supplied by the Turkish team were not tested for the evaluation of the internal bond, since they were severely damaged during the cutting phase, making it practically impossible to prepare the samples for the IB tests.

Figure 1 a , b. Aspect of one of the panels prepared by the Swedish team, on which the internal bond was measured. The plywood panel underlying the insulating panel was removed before cutting and testing.

Square specimens of approximately 50 mm side and thickness equal to the thickness of the panel were prepared from the two panels. Once prepared, they were allowed to equilibrate in a standard climate (20°C and 65% RH) for one week.

These specimens were used to measure in turn:

- density, by measuring the mass and dimensions of the specimen using a centesimal calliper. Due to an error, the density was not measured directly on the panel 1 specimens. In this case, the values were measured on a separate set of specimens and the average value was applied to them;
- IB, according to standard EN 319:1993 “Particleboards and fibreboards - Determination of tensile strength perpendicular to the plane of the board” (Figure 2).

Figure 2a, b. Typical arrangement of tests for internal bond measurement. Left, initial configuration; right, failure mode. The samples shown in the pictures do not represent the specimens tested from the panel.

2.3 Results

The values of density and IB strength for the individual specimens prepared from the two panels are shown in

Table 1. The average IB values were the same for the two panels, while the average density values differed by only about 5%. This indicates that the procedures used to prepare panels were quite well reproducible.

Table 1. Individual values obtained for internal bond and density for the two panels produced by the Swedish team. Values marked with '*' refer to the average value of measurements made a separate set of specimens.

Specimen Id.	Max load, N	Stress at max, MPa	Density, g/cm ³
P1-1	106.0	0.04	0.688 *
P1-2	152.0	0.06	0.688 *
P1-3	171.9	0.07	0.688 *
P1-5	141.8	0.06	0.688 *
P1-6	145.6	0.06	0.688 *
P1-7	114.0	0.05	0.688 *
Average value ± standard deviation		0.06 ± 0.01	0.688 ± 0,007
P2-1	122.0	0.05	0.653
P2-2	121.1	0.05	0.653
P2-3	138.0	0.06	0.611
P2-4	164.3	0.07	0.666
P2-5	127.4	0.05	0.675
P2-7	152.7	0.06	0.660
Average value ± standard deviation		0.06 ± 0.01	0.653 ± 0.022

The strength values obtained are obviously very low for a standard particleboard panel, but it should be borne in mind that these are insulation panels for which no specific cohesive strength requirements are normally specified. However, the data also show that the panels were internally quite homogeneous, i.e. characterised by limited variation along the panel plane. In fact, the coefficient of variation (CV) of density was less than 3.5% for both panels, indicating a homogeneous distribution of the various constituents in the plane. IB was slightly more variable, with CVs of 18% and 13% for panels P1 and P2, respectively. This difference, which is not apparent from the data shown in

Table 1, is due to an approximation of the data reported in the table. However, strength values can usually be even more variable for particleboard, so the reported data can be taken as confirmation of the homogeneity of panel production.

Figure 3. Curves of storage modulus (E') and TandDelta ($\tan\delta$) for representative samples of each of the five treatments considered, in comparison to untreated wood (indicated with C in the caption of the Figure).

- The values of E' are extremely variable. At 20°C, it ranges from approx. 4,000 MPa for MP treatment to approx. 12,000 MPa for EST, to be compared with approx. 9,000 for the untreated reference wood. Even considering the natural variability that always characterizes stiffness in wood, this difference highlights that the treatments are able to modify this parameter, in some cases improving it (at room temperature) as happens for EST, in others worsening it, as is the case for MP.
- The treatments are able to modify the behavior of stiffness with temperature, although to different degrees. In fact, looking at the curve of E' for untreated wood, it is possible observing the substantial invariance of this parameter, at least in the temperature range considered (Figure 17). For all the products, however, a decrease in E' is observed, more or less marked depending on the specific PCM.

Further interesting considerations emerge if we look at the curve of the $\tan\delta$ with temperature. In this case it is possible to highlight that:

- Despite the decrease in moisture that certainly affects the material in passing from 10 °C to 40 °C, the $\tan\delta$ for untreated wood undergoes appreciably lower variations than those observed for the treated material. For untreated wood, these variations are most likely related to the evaporation of water, which is known to have plasticizing action for the cell walls of wood.
- For the two esters that are present between the considered products (EST and MP) a peak in the $\tan\delta$ curve is observed, at very similar temperatures for both products (27.8°C for EST and 26.5°C for MP).
- In the other products, on the other hand, the maxima observed are much wider (broad curves) and lower than the maxima observed for the two esters. The behavior between the three products (LA, LO/COFA, CA) is overall quite similar, with values initially (i.e. at low temperatures) high, and then increasingly lower as temperature increases, although the temperature associated with this lowering is different between the three.

As expected, the variations with temperature in the curves of the two parameters (E' and $\tan\delta$) are associated with each other, so the decrease in E' is more pronounced the sharper the peak of $\tan\delta$. Consequently, only for the two esters it is possible observe a clear molecular relaxation, to

be associated with some form of substantial modification (for example a transition) of the impregnation material (and not in wood). In contrast, for the other products the changes are more limited or in any case less impactful on the mechanical characteristics of the treated materials. In this regard, it is possible to make an additional consideration. The fact that the application of a product has influenced the viscoelastic characteristics of the treated wood implies that the same product has not only filled the cell lumen but has somehow interacted with the biopolymers that make up the wood, and this denotes that there has been a penetration within the cell walls. However, it is not possible to determine with this technique how much the product has been able to penetrate.

Figure 4. Trend of storage modulus (E') and $\text{Tan}\Delta$ ($\tan\delta$) for representative samples treated with a mixture of modified coconut oil and linoleic fatty acids (LO) as such and subjected to preheating at 100 °C. The curves were also compared with untreated wood (indicated by C in the caption of the Figure).

Further considerations can be made if the effect of preheating at 100 °C of the treated material is taken into account.

In particular, by preheating the LO series (Figure 18) it can be verified that the curves of both E' and $\tan\delta$ are very similar to those of the unheated polymer. The differences found in the absolute values of these parameters (e.g. at 20 °C, E' is approx. 8,000 for the preheated material and approx. 9,000 MPa for the unheated one) are to be attributed more to the natural variability that characterizes all the mechanical characteristics of the wood than to anything else. It is also interesting to note that the peak of $\tan\delta$ occurs in both cases at very similar values of temperature (approx. 12.5 °C).

On the other hand, by preheating the EST series (Figure 19) substantial differences are noted. In particular, the value of E' at 20 °C decreases from 12,500 MPa to 7,500 MPa and the behavior with the temperature changes considerably. In fact, the substantial decrease of E' with temperature observed in the unheated sample is less evident in the preheated material; moreover, in the latter the modulus reaches the zone of substantial invariance around 25 °C, unlike the unheated material where this area is reached at about 30 °C.

These differences are most evident when looking at the $\tan\delta$ curves. The big peak centered at approx. 28 °C, which is very evident in the unheated material, is much less apparent in the preheated sample, in which instead a relaxation occurs around approx. 17 °C.

These circumstances indicate how high-temperature preheating has changed the interaction between wood and polymer substantially. Most likely, the ester in those conditions moves away (e.g. by evaporation) or even reacts, and this leads to a modification of the rheological behavior of the treated wood, leading to a less viscous behavior.

Between the two hypotheses, considering that:

- if the ester acted as a plasticizer it should lead to a lowering of both E' and the $\tan\delta$ peak temperature,
- that instead the value of E' decreases after preheating,
- the trend with temperature also worsens after preheating,

the hypothesis of simple evaporation should be discarded. This implies that preheating could lead to a substantial change in the properties of the polymer as a result, for example, of a possible

reaction. This hypothesis should of course be confirmed with additional tests, if deemed of interest.

Figure 5. Curves of storage modulus (E') and $\text{Tan}\delta$ ($\tan\delta$) for representative samples treated with palmitic acid methyl ester (EST), as such and subjected to preheating at 100 °C. The curves are compared with untreated wood (indicated by C in the caption of the Figure).

2.4 References

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3 OR4 (WP 3-4) Valutazione della durabilità alle muffe in condizioni di laboratorio dei bio-compositi con PCM.

Evaluation of resistance of bio-composites impregnated with PCM against moulds

3.1 Introduction

The evaluation against moulds was performed following, with some modifications, the standard E24-06 AWPA (American Wood Protection Association Standard) 2008 titled Standard method of evaluating the resistance of wood product surfaces to mold growth.

The aim of this standard is determining the relative resistance of wood based products to surface growth of moulds in an environment favourable for growth of moulds. Resistance to moulds growth is evaluated relative to unprotected sapwood of *Pinus sylvestris*.

This standard was designed to evaluate the resistance of the surfaces of wooden products, treated or untreated, coated or uncoated, to the growth of mould. The main objective of the method is to determine the relative resistance of wood products to surface mold growth in an environment conducive to the growth of fungi.

Samples of wood products are exhibited in an environmental chamber where temperature is relative humidity is controlled to provide ideal conditions for mold growth. The chamber and samples are inoculated with the specified molds and the air circulation within the chamber continuously subjects the samples to the spores for the duration of the test. The method is not sterile and therefore forms from the air or soil may be present and compete with the inoculated molds for colonization on product test surfaces. For controls, samples are removed from the chamber and evaluated for mold growth on the sample surfaces every two weeks to eight weeks. Each sample is given an assessment of the extent and intensity of mold growth. The results for the replicate samples are calculated and compared with results obtained for the reference products and untreated samples to evaluate the relative resistance of the products to growth modeling.

3.2 Material and methods

The samples of dimensions 75 x 100 mm were:

1. Untreated sapwood Scots pine

2. Swedish bio-composites (BPCM) were based on Ethyl palmitate ester (EP) 25% ,hardwood and sapwood particles 25 %, 12,5 % of untreated newspaper and 37, 5 % of epoxidized linseed oil as binder. The density of bio-composites pressed was 740 Kg/ m³.
3. Turkish bio-composites were Capric acid (CP) 40 % and wood fibres 40% and starch as binder 20% were used , density 300 Kg /m³.

The Swedish BPCM were obtained two by from three different panels. The name id due to PCM (EP or CP) used , number 1, 2 or 3 due to different panel from which is obtained and 1 or 2 number pf two samples for panel. For each bio-composites and untreated Scots pine samples 6 replicates were used.

The modification was that the box was placed in a conditionate room 75 % RH (relative humidity) and 28 °C Temperature so the small fan applied as described in the standard was unusual and instead of pitched box it was used a flat box.

Figure 1. The gray colored samples are the PCMs created by the Swedish partner; the brown colored samples are PCMs created by the turkish partner and the light wood samples are from *Pinus sylvestris*.

For carrying out this method a special box is built. The box was in plexiglass with a bottom container of soil and peat and where the spores of moulds were distributed. In the chamber were placed some holding bars with support for wood and bio-composites samples (Figure 1).

a plexiglass chamber was assembled in our carpentry laboratories and set up with all its components to encourage the growth of moulds: with a fan for air circulation, a substrate for containing the peat and the special shelves for maintaining the test samples (Figure 2).

Each bio-composites and reference untreated pine samples were six. The moulds utilized were *Aerobasidium pullulans*, *Penicillium spp*, *Sydowia polyspora*, *Trichoderma viride*.

The moulds were inoculated in the Petri dishes and then , after sporulation transferred in the soils.

Figure 2a Box in plexiglass for evaluating the resistance to moulds of bio-composites. Top view

Figure 2b Box in plexiglass for evaluating the resistance to moulds of bio-composites. Frontal view

The results were , in accordance to ranking described in table 1 , after 2, 4, 6 and 8 weeks are reported in the table 2.

Table 2 Rating for evaluating mould resistance

RATING	DESCRIPTION
0	No visible growth
1	Mold covering up to 10% of surfaces providing growth is not so intense or colored as to obscure the sample color over more than 5% of surfaces
2	Mold covering between 10% and 30% of surfaces providing growth is not so intense or colored as to obscure the sample color on more than 10% of surfaces

3	Mold covering between 30% and 70% of surfaces providing growth is not so intense or colored as to obscure the sample color on more than 30% of surfaces
4	Mold on greater than 70% of surfaces providing growth is not so intense or colored as to obscure the sample color over more than 70% of surfaces
5	Mold on 100% of surfaces or with less than 100% coverage and with intense or colored growth obscuring greater than 70% of the sample color

Table 3 Results

Swedish bio-composite	First check (after 2 week by beginning)	Second checks (after 4 weeks)	Third check (after 8 weeks)
EP2-1	1		
EP3-2	1		
EP1-2	1		
EP3-1	0/1		
EP2-2	0/1		
EP1-1	0/1		
Turkish bio-composites			
MP11	1 (Rotto)	/	
MP12	0	0	4
MP1	1 (Rotto)	/	
MP31	3	3	5
MP32	3	3	5
MP22	3	3	4
Untreated Scots pine reference sample			
C1	4	4	5
C2	4	4	5
C3	2	2	5
C4	3	4	4
C5	1	3	5
C6	3	3	5

The chamber conditions were set at a temperature of 25°C and a humidity of 90-98%.

For the preparation of the spores for the mold cultures, three solutions of 1 liter each one were prepared with the following inoculums (Figure 28):

- *Aureobasidium pullulans* (d. By.) Arnaud, ATCC 9348;
- *Aspergillus niger* v. Tiegh, ATCC 6275.

Figure 4: Spores for the mold cultures.

For controls, samples are removed from the chamber and evaluated for mold growth on the sample surfaces every two weeks to eight weeks (Figure 5).

Figure 5. First control after two weeks.

4 OR4 (WP 3-4) Valutazione della durabilità ai funghi della carie in condizioni di laboratorio dei bio-compositi con PCM.

Evaluation of biological resistance against fungal decay in accordance with EN 113-3 (Durability of wood and wood-based products — Test method against wood destroying basidiomycetes — Part 3: Assessment of durability of wood based panels) of two bio-composites impregnated with PCM.

4.1 Introduction

The European standard EN 113-3 describes a laboratory test method in which small samples of the wood-based panel product under test are exposed to attack by a range of wood-destroying basidiomycete fungi in pure culture. The thickness of the test specimens varies, since it is dictated by the thickness of the wood based panel product under test.

4.2 Materials and methods

The two bio-composites used are:

The bio-composites samples of dimensions 50 x 50 mm were:

1. Swedish (S) bio-composites (BPCM) were based on Ethyl palmitate ester (EP) 25% ,hardwood and sapwood particles 25 %, 12,5 % of untreated newspaper and 37, 5 % of epoxidized linseed oil as binder. The density of bio-composites pressed was 740 Kg/ m³.
2. Turkish (T) bio-composites were Capric acid (CP) 40 % and wood fibres 40% and starch as binder 20% were used , density 300 Kg /m³.
3. As reference samples were used 25 x 15 x 50 samples respectively of Scots pine and Beech.

Due to the risk of leaching or chemical decomposition of PCM impregnated into bio-composites we didn't obtain directly the dry weight on the samples that then put in contact with fungi but on a group consisted respectively by S and T bio-composites in order to determine the theoretical average dry weight to apply in the calculation of final mass loss.

Further the virulence of fungi was tested on the beech and Scots pine samples put in contact with the fungi. The duration of the biological test (contact with fungi) is 16 weeks.

The results is based on the mass loss calculated on percentage of final dry mass with respect to initial theoretical one for bio-composites, instead effective for virulence controls.

$$ML \% = [(Mi - Mf) / Mi] \times 100$$

The fungus utilized were:

C. puteana

P. ostearus

T. Versicolor

The results shall be accepted as valid provided that the virulence control specimens) have lost more than the minimum value given in EN 113-3.

The theoretical initial mass was determined on five samples for each bio-composites as reported in the table 1

TABLE 1 Theoretical initial dry mass

BIO_COMPOSITE	Initial weight (g)	Dry weight (g)	MC*
1 T	12,64	5,22	142,15
2T	13,96	6,54	113,46
3T	11,71	4,30	172,33
4T	12,28	4,86	152,67
5T	10,87	3,45	215,07
	<i>media</i>	4,87	
	<i>dev st</i>	1,15	
P1-4	21,5	20,51	4,83
P1-17	22,44	21,45	4,62
P1-8	22,05	21,06	4,70
P2-5	21,17	20,18	4,91
P1-9	22,7	21,71	4,56
	<i>media</i>	20,98	
	<i>dev st</i>	0,64	

Due the easy of leaching of oils on T bio-composites the value of MC it was not considered realistic.

As average value for the fungal test it was used the average value of both.

Figure 2. Controls specimens by *Fagus sylvatica* on the left and *Pinus sylvestris* on the right.

Figure 3. Turkish specimens.

Figure 4. Swedish specimens.

The results expressed in mass loss are reported in table 2, where are reported the virulence against the fungi utilized. As it possible to observe only the Swedish bio-composites are resistant to Fungal decay, instead the Turkish ones had a mass loss percentage higher than virulence control.

TABLE 2 Virulence on Scots pine and beech and Mass loss % on bio-composites.

Scots pine virulence	Average	Standard deviation	N
<i>T. versicolor</i>	26,1	3,6	4
<i>P. oteatrus</i>	33,6	2,8	4
Beech virulence	Average	Standard deviation	N
<i>T. versicolor</i>	33,7	5,4	3
<i>P. oteatrus</i>	28,8	9,1	4
Biocomposites	ML	dev.st	
Turkish	Average	Standard deviation	N
<i>T. versicolor</i>	70,2	4,3	
<i>P. oteatrus</i>	67,0	7,6	
<i>C.puteana</i>	67,3	4,9	
Swedish	Average	Standard deviation	N
<i>T. versicolor</i>	5,0	0,2	
<i>P. oteatrus</i>	5,2	0,4	
<i>C.puteana</i>	5,3	0,3	

Figure 5a,b,c,d,e,f Samples and virulence controls and after the time in contact with fungi.

5 OR4 (WP 3-4) Valutazione della durabilità alle termiti in condizioni di laboratorio dei bio-compositi con PCM. Determination of biological resistance against termites of bio-composites impregnated with PCM in accordance with European standard EN 117.

5.1 Description of different steps for assembling the test

The work carried out with subterranean termites, Italian species *Reticulitermes lucifugus*, can be described in the following steps:

1. Finding of termites (*Reticulitermes sp.*) in the field.

This genus develops its nest in the ground and is organized in castes formed by individuals with distinct functions.

Workers: they represent the largest caste and are responsible for providing food to all other members by degrading wood. They are sterile and without wing. Length of 3-6 mm, whitish. -

Soldiers: characterized by a leader with evident jaws, they have a defense function. They are sterile and atteri.

Reproducers: primary (winged), flicker in spring and found a new colony; Substitution secondaries, neotenic, can found new colonies in particular situations. - Nymphs: undifferentiated juvenile individuals.

2. Materials and methods

The evaluation of resistance to subterranean termites, Italian species, *Reticulitermes lucifugus*, was carried out in accordance with European normative EN 117. Wood preservatives - Determination of toxic values against *Reticulitermes* species (European termites)(Laboratory method) 2023.

The test, based on an artificial mini-colony, 250 workers with some soldiers and nymphs in percentage depending on original colony, is put in contact with the PMC impregnated samples for eight weeks or until that all the termites in treated samples was died. The PMC impregnated wood samples were six replicates for treatments and was used nine untreated reference controls.

The validity of test was based on percentage of workers put in contact with untreated Scots pine samples, the test is considered valid only if the survival is almost the 50%. The evaluation of decay was determined based on a four grades ranking that considers the extension and the depth of galleries excavates by termites into the wood and on their survival. The results can be also expressed as Durability class as reported in EN 350: 2016. This durability assessment is based on the percentages, between the replicates for a same treatment, of different ranking grades. If the grade of attack is 0 or 1 for more than 90% of samples and the remaining 10% is not more than 2 the treatments is durable. When the ranking 3 or 4 is less than 50% the durability class is moderately durable, finally if the same ranking grades are equal or more than 50% the durability class is non-durable.

The samples deriving from bio-composite panels based on wood fiber and PCM are 5 for each product; The untreated control samples, necessary to verify the virulence of the termites taken for testing, are 3, and the species used as a reference was pine.

The results are expressed in accordance with the following table:

0) no attack;

1) attempted attack:

i) superficial erosion of insufficient depth to be measured on an unlimited area of the test specimen; or ii) attack to a depth of 0,5 mm provided that this is restricted to an areas not more than 30 mm² in total; or iii) combination of i) and ii)

2) slight attack: i) erosion of ≤ 1 mm in depth limited to not more than 1/10 of the surface of the test specimen; or ii) single tunnelling to a depth of up to 3 mm; or iii) combination of i) and ii)

3) average attack: i) erosion of ≤ 1 mm in depth over more than 1/10 of the surface area of the test specimen; or ii) erosion of > 1 mm to < 3 mm in depth limited to not more than 1/10 of the surface of the test specimen; or iii) isolated tunneling of a depth > 3 mm not enlarging to form cavities; or iii) any combination of i), ii) or iii);

4) strong attack:

i) erosion of > 1 mm to < 3 mm in depth of more than 1/10 of the surface of the test specimen; or ii) tunneling penetrating to a depth > 3 mm and enlarging to form a cavity in the body of the test specimen; or iii) combination of i) and ii).

The insects are collected individually, using small brushes, and counted until they form groups of 250 individuals, discarding those that appear injured or dying. In each group a number of soldiers is added in proportion to those found in the colony from which the workers were taken.

3. Exposure of samples to termites.
Preparation of container

Each group of 250 individuals is lowered into a container containing water, sand (in the proportions of one volume of water for every four volumes of sand), a glass ring in the center and a small piece of wood from the original colony. After a day, a test sample is laid over the ring. Each jar is closed and taken to the well-ventilated air-conditioned chamber at about 26 ± 2 °C, and with a relative humidity of 70 ± 5 %.

4. Control of tests.

Samples are monitored for up to 8 weeks. To confirm that the termites have adapted appropriately, it can be noted their movement in the sandy substrate, clearly visible in particular at the edges of the walls of the jar.

Where it is not possible to see if the termites are still alive, the jar is opened and emptied; in case of activity it is recomposed, otherwise the test is considered finished.

5.2 Results

Through visual inspection each specimen is evaluated according to the presence of attack, its extension and depth.

Expression of visual examination results:

Beginning date	Sample / PCM/ kind of bio-composite	Survival of termites (weeks)	Attack ranking	Notes
Turkish NO PMC				
21-giu	1 k2	3	0 No attack	
21-giu	2 k2	3	0 No attack	
21-giu	3 k2	3	0 No attack	
21-giu	4 k2	3	0 No attack	
21-giu	5 k2	3	4 Strong attack	
LA/ Turkish				
21-giu	1LA	3	0 No attack	
21-giu	2LA	2	0 No attack	Moulds
21-giu	3LA	2	0 No attack	Moulds
21-giu	4LA	3	0 No attack	Moulds
21-giu	5LA	3	0 No attack	
MP/Turkish				
23-giu	1MP	3	0 No attack	
23-giu	2MP	3	0 No attack	
23-giu	3MP	3	0 No attack	
23-giu	4MP	4	0 No attack	Moulds
23-giu	5MP	3	0 No attack	
CA/Turkish				
27-giu	1CA	3	0 No attack	
27-giu	2CA	3	0 No attack	
27-giu	3CA	2	0 No attack	
27-giu	4CA	2	0 No attack	
27-giu	5CA	1	0 No attack	
EP/ Swedish				
22-giu	1S	2	0 No attack	
22-giu	2S	2	0 No attack	
22-giu	3S	2	0 No attack	
22-giu	4S	3	0 No attack	
22-giu	5S	3	0 No attack	
Untreated control				
28-giu	1P	28-aug		Checked alive until 8 august
28-giu	2P	28-aug		Checked alive until 8 august
28-giu	3P	28-aug		Checked alive until 8 august

Images of the specimens bio-composites based on wood fibre and PCM, at the end of the test

Figure 6 Front side bio-composites at the end of test

Figure 7 back side bio-composites at the end of test

Figure 8 Untreated reference control specimens

5.3 Conclusions

All specimens derived from bio-composite panels based on wood fiber and PCM were resistant to attack by termites, with the exception of a single specimen (5k2) which had a small tunnel > depth 1 mm, without any other cavity. The validity of the tests is confirmed by the severe attacks suffered by the untreated pine control samples. The untreated specimens were maintained in the containers until the end of test, and they were attacked until 4 degree.

6 OR1 (WP 4.2) Realization of fungal mycelium with PCM prototypes

During the BIO NRG STORE project, given the high importance of the topic of our test laboratories and PCMs, for the development of prototypes based on fungal mycelium and PCM was agreed with the project partners.

The research phases are still ongoing and the design results are being worked on and studied by testing the properties of these fungal prototypes.

The development and research phases are as follow:

- Creation of the spawn for the propagation of the fungal mycelium (Figure.30);

Figure 1. Spawn for the propagation of the fungal mycelium

- Creation of bags containing PCM biomass and fungal mycelium for the propagation of the material (Figure.1);

Figure 2: Bags containing PCM biomass and fungal mycelium

- Development of the panel based on fungal mycelium and PCM (Figure 2);

Figure 3. Panels based on fungal mycelium and PCM.

- Final panel dried (Figure 3);

Figure 4. Final fungal and PCM panel dried.